

Studies on Viscosity and Density Behaviour of Concentrated Solutions of Chloroacetic Acids in Aqueous Ethanol

P. S. NIKAM* and MEHDI HASAN

P. G. Department of Physical Chemistry, M.S.G. College, Malegaon-Camp-423 105

Manuscript received 13 May 1990, revised 13 April 1992, accepted 21 April 1992

Viscosity and density measurements have been made on systems comprising mono- di- and trichloroacetic acids (concentration range 0.1–1.0 M) in aqueous ethanol at 30 and 36°. The data have been used to calculate viscosity B -coefficients employing Breslau-Miller, Vand and Thomas equations. Apparent molar volumes have also been obtained from density measurements. The structure-promoting behaviour has been found to follow the order, mono- < di- < trichloroacetic acid.

Measurements of viscosities and apparent molar volumes of electrolytes in solutions provide an excellent method of obtaining data on solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions. These interactions have been studied in aqueous and nonaqueous solutions by many workers but such investigations in mixed solvents are scanty. The Jones-Dole¹ equation accounts for the observed viscosity-concentration dependence of dilute electrolyte solutions, while Breslau-Miller², Vand³ and Thomas⁴ equations account for the concentration dependence of viscosity in concentrated electrolyte solutions. In continuation of our earlier studies^{5–8}, we now report the changes brought in the structure of solvent (water-ethanol) on the addition of mono-, di- and trichloroacetic acids.

Results and Discussion

Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and relative viscosity (η_r) of MCAA, DCAA and TCAA solutions in different compositions of water-ethanol were determined at 30 and 36°. The relative viscosity data are analysed with the help of Breslau-Miller equation², Vand equation³ and Thomas equation⁴ as reported earlier⁹. Representative graphs of Vand and Thomas equations are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively.

B -values obtained from these equations (Table 1) are more or less identical. The close examination of the data shows that (i) B -coefficients are positive and decrease with ethanol content in MCAA solutions. They become negative in 34.4 and 54.1 wt% ethanol solutions. This suggests that structure-making tendency of MCAA decreases with increase of ethanol, (ii) in DCAA solutions the positive B -coefficient decreases with increase of ethanol content, becomes minimum in 25.3 wt% ethanol solution and then increases with further increase of ethanol content, and trend suggests that the aqueous ethanol has a minimum structuredness in 25.3 wt% ethanol mixture in presence of DCAA, and (iii) in TCAA solutions the positive and large B -values indicate

Fig. 1. Plots of $C/\log \eta_r$ vs C for TCAA at 30°.

that TCAA functions as strong structure maker in all the solvent mixtures. It is interesting to note further that B -value does not vary much with ethanol content indicating the same structuredness of the aqueous ethanol solvent mixture in the presence of TCAA. The effect of interaction between chloroacetic acids and solvent molecules results in the formation of $\text{Cl}\cdots\text{O}=\text{H}$ linkages due to break up of hydrogen bonds in aggregates ethanol and water.

The structure-making tendency of the acids follows the order, $\text{MCAA} < \text{DCAA} < \text{TCAA}$ as evidenced by $B_{\text{MCAA}} < B_{\text{DCAA}} < B_{\text{TCAA}}$.

The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) calculated from the density data varied linearly with the square-root of concentration in conformity with Masson's

 Fig. 2. Plots of $(\eta_r - 1)/C$ vs C for TCAA at 30° .

TABLE 1—VALUES OF B FROM VARIOUS EQUATIONS						
Ethanol (wt %)	B_1	B_2	B_3	B		
				B_1	B_2	B_3
MCAA						
	30°			36°		
0.0	0.116	0.134	0.110	0.105	0.124	0.100
8.0	0.102	0.080	0.077	0.111	0.080	0.059
16.4	0.061	0.081	0.036	0.062	0.082	0.060
25.3	0.012	—	—	0.021	—	—
34.4	-0.008	—	-0.021	-0.006	—	-0.014
54.1	-0.040	—	-0.075	-0.022	—	-0.064
DCAA						
0.0	0.209	0.218	0.214	0.197	0.205	0.204
8.0	0.192	0.220	0.198	0.182	0.198	0.184
16.4	0.120	0.134	0.142	0.118	0.126	0.141
25.3	0.048	0.051	0.042	0.050	0.063	0.051
34.4	0.048	0.078	0.077	0.052	0.075	0.078
54.1	0.075	0.125	0.131	0.088	0.135	0.126
TCAA						
0.0	0.228	0.245	0.230	0.202	0.255	0.232
8.0	0.295	0.308	0.258	0.286	0.290	0.250
16.4	0.278	0.285	0.285	0.289	0.285	0.285
25.3	0.284	0.288	0.285	0.278	0.275	0.282
34.4	0.284	0.285	0.285	0.289	0.290	0.290
54.1	0.197	0.202	0.202	0.200	0.205	0.205

B_1 from Breslau-Miller equation; B_2 from Vand's equation; B_3 from Thomas equation.

equation¹⁰,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (1)$$

The values of apparent molar volume at infinite dilution ($\phi_v^0 = \bar{V}_v^0$) and the slope (S_v) for the acids are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS OF MASSON EQUATION						
Ethanol (wt %)	ϕ_v^0	S_v	ϕ_v^0	S_v	ϕ_v^0	S_v
30°						
30°						
0.0	60.66	1.92	68.80	4.93	78.45	7.14
8.0	59.40	3.49	69.10	5.75	77.45	8.24
16.4	58.90	4.46	72.60	4.46	85.10	10.87
25.3	62.20	3.60	70.20	10.36	86.80	7.32
34.4	59.20	6.48	71.70	10.00	89.30	10.39
54.1	60.70	6.02	76.50	5.27	94.30	11.05
36°						
0.0	62.36	2.00	70.30	4.69	81.20	7.00
8.0	61.10	2.69	71.50	4.57	79.00	7.92
16.4	59.10	5.18	75.10	3.18	88.70	7.67
25.3	62.10	3.06	72.10	10.36	87.50	6.26
34.4	59.20	5.06	76.50	10.00	90.15	10.75
54.1	60.70	5.61	77.95	5.27	98.20	7.86

The \bar{V}_v^0 of MCAA, DCAA and TCAA are the sum of their ionic partial molar volumes¹¹, $\bar{V}_{H^+}^0$ and $\bar{V}_{CAA^-}^0$ (where V_{CAA^-} is the ionic partial molar volumes of chloroacetate ions) as

$$\bar{V}_{acid}^0 = \bar{V}_{H^+}^0 + \bar{V}_{CAA^-}^0 \quad (2)$$

When a solute is introduced into a polar solvent, the partial molar volume of the solute at infinite dilution (\bar{V}_v^0), can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}_{acid}^0 &= \bar{V}_{H^+}^0 + \bar{V}_{CAA^-}^0 \\ &= V_{H^+(int)} + V_{CAA^-(int)} + \Delta V \\ &= V_{H^+(int)} + V_{CAA^-(int)} + \Delta(H+Solvation) \\ &\quad + \Delta V(CAA-Solvation) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $V_{H^+(int)}$ and $V_{CAA^-(int)}$ are intrinsic volumes of the ions and ΔV is the change in volume of the system due to ion-solvent interactions. In solutions of MCAA, DCAA and TCAA in water-ethanol, it can be assumed¹¹⁻¹⁴ that in the case of chloroacetate ions (CAA^-) due to their large size, $V_{CAA^-(int)}$ has negligible solvation [$\Delta V_{(CAA^-Solvation)}$] in comparison to the proton [$\Delta V_{(H+Solvation)}$]. In other words, the ΔV term in equation (3) is mainly due to proton solvation. The change of partial molar volumes (\bar{V}_v^0) with composition of the mixed solvent can be explained on variable solvation of ions¹⁵. The $\phi_v^0 (= \bar{V}_{acid}^0)$ values follow the order, MCAA < DCAA < TCAA at each solvent composition. However due to the large size of the anions, the values of \bar{V}_{acid}^0 of the chloroacetic acid are determined by the term $V_{CAA^-(int)}$ and $\Delta V_{(H+Solvation)}$,

since $V_{H^+(Int)}$ and $\Delta V_{(CAA-Solvation)}$ are negligible in water, ethanol and their mixtures. Greater the size of the anion ($V_{CAA^-(Int)}$), higher is the ϕ_v^0 value. So the trend in $\phi_v^0(\bar{V}_{acid}^0)$ parallels the anionic size. This is also supported from viscosity B -coefficients.

The positive S_v values show that the electrolytes will be appreciably associated and would result in the weakening of the solute-solvent interaction. In salts containing ions of small radii and compact nature there is no interionic penetration¹⁶. However in chloroacetate ions which are quite large, there is a possibility of strong electrostatic ion-ion interaction and therefore positive values of S_v are expected.

Experimental

Monochloroacetic acid (MCAA), dichloroacetic acid (DCAA) and ethanol were purified as reported earlier^{7,8}. Triple-distilled water was used. Trichloroacetic acid (TCAA) was purified by recrystallising it from chloroform¹⁷. Water and ethanol were mixed (by weight) to give mixtures of different dielectric constants¹⁸. Solutions of different molarities were prepared afresh by dissolving the acid in solvent mixture. The experimental set-up and methods used for measuring density and viscosity were similar to those reported earlier^{9,10}. The reproducibility in density and viscosity measurement was $\pm 0.0001 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$ and $\pm 0.0003 \text{ cP}$ respectively. The temperature measurements were accurate within $\pm 0.01^\circ$.

Acknowledgement

Authors thank Principal S. S. Patil for facilities.

References

1. G. JONES and M. DOLE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
2. B. R. BRESLAU and J. F. MILLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 1056.
3. V. VAND, *J. Phys. Colloid Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 277, 314
4. D. J. THOMAS, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1965, **20**, 267.
5. P. S. NIKAM and M. HASAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1948, **53**, 260
6. P. S. NIKAM and M. HASAN, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1986, **24**, 502.
7. P. S. NIKAM and M. HASAN, *J. Chem. Eng Data*, 1988, **33**, 165.
8. P. S. NIKAM and M. HASAN, *J. Acoust. Soc. India*, 1990, **3-4**, 122.
9. P. S. NIKAM and A. R. HIRAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 883.
10. D. O. MASSON, *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, **8**, 218.
11. U. SEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1976, **80**, 1566.
12. J. BERNAL and R. FOWLER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, **1**, 515.
13. R. H. STOKES and E. A. ROBINSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **70**, 1870.
14. P. S. NIKAM and A. R. HIRAY, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1992, **4**, 176.
15. R. L. BATEMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2291; 1952, **74**, 5516.
16. R. GOPAL, D. K. AGRAWAL and R. KUMAR, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, **84**, 141.
17. W. S. LAYNE, H. H. JAYNE and H. ZIMMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 435.
18. A. K. MANDAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15**, 728.
19. P. S. NIKAM and A. R. HIRAY, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1988, **26**, 37.